

Teacher's role in career perception

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Abstract

The purpose of this research work is to study the role of the teacher's inside the school in creating the career perception offer (10+2) students. This research work is an empirical study. Data collected through specific standardized psychological test. The study completed for various disciplines. Obtained results showed that teacher's role is important and beneficial. In this regard, career perceptions are formulated through various process and affected by different factors and variables. The details of findings are discussed in this present paper.

Key Words:-Teachers cooperation, career perception, factors, disciplines, globalizing, Internationalizing, creating Identified, Market Forces.

Introduction

Present scenario of education indicates the confusing state of job opportunity among students. Students who have passed (10+2) or its equivalent do not understand their career scope for future. They go to their teachers and friends to talk on selecting the discipline but found hopeless answer. At last, they choose unwanted subject or discipline or choose those types of subjects in which they have less interest. When they go to the colleges or higher institutions they find themselves helpless. Some students who have taken admission in various disciplines as medical, engineering, law, management or science stream but the students of other than science discipline do not have shy cognizance among college students. They become frustrate and miss their target. Deciding about ones future is not quite easy. The task becomes even more complex when one's have so much information, so many people whose opinions one's cannot ignore, stiff competition to encounter and so many pressure to cape with. The process of career planning stretches through the secondary and senior secondary years at school. It essentially requires an adequate understanding of one self in terms of academic potentials, attributes, talents, interests, personality, values, expectations and resources. This basic-understanding helps in location of suitable options. It has been observed that when planned routes to a career perception or optional careers are chalked out during school, years, keeping in mind all attributes preparations to inter a course and career are adequately motivated and effective. The motivation stirs the yond through preparation, study, competition and self-confidence and teacher guidance and cooperation's. Good career planning envisages a match between requirements for a job, aptitudes, interest, personality, and expectation and teacher cooperation's. Awareness of "true" motivation, aspiration, strengths, dislikes, limitations, weaknesses and teacher cooperation's or guidance are essential. This awareness must be as specific as possible. It must be backed by actual achievements and behaviors and if required, supplemented by objective test results. The test results however, are often used to loosely for giving judgment on suitability of career perception or career option's. The teachers play significant role in shaping career decision making capacity or career perception and choice and more important factor in shaping the lives of their students.

In the vast world scenario of education, a teacher's role goes beyond just important facts: it involves shaping the future of each student's. One greater aspect of this responsibility is career counselling or teacher cooperation inside the school, where the teacher cooperate and guidance provided by teacher becomes a crucial compass and helping students navigate for the complexities of decision making career choices. Teachers help as mentors and

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offering valuable understanding, insights for the strengths, weakness and interest of their own self in students. Creating by teachers an open and supportive environment and they find a deep understanding of every student's aspirations, fears and intellectuality. The personal connection of teachers enables to provide exact career perception and steering students towards path that combine with their individuality. In the process of teacher cooperation teacher act as a mentor, career counsellor, communications, identification of strengths and weaknesses, provider of information, inspiratory and motivator and also helps career counselling initiatives thoughts and work. Teacher encouraging students to explore diversity fields of study for career path. Teacher can create an atmosphere that fosters curiosity and experimentation to allow the students to make their career decisions and discover their passions. This exploration phase is vast for students to make decisions about their academic, professionals and career perception pursuits. Career perception or decisions often come with a desirable or considerable thoughts of uncertainty. Thus teachers play an important role in building the confidence of their students. By providing positive thoughts and reinforcement, constructive five feedback and nurturing a growth mind set and teachers empowered students to face the problems, challenges of career exploration with self-confidence. For success in any career teachers also play a significant role in nurturing soft skills essential for career perception. Adaptability, problem solving, team work and communication are important skills that teachers can in still in their students. These skills are the foundation for a successful career perception. The guidance, support and inspiration provided by teacher's inside the school produce confidence and motivation in students as they explore various career options and possibilities.

Review of literature

The aims of the present study conducted on a correlational study of relationship between teacher's cooperation in-side the school and creation of career perception of student's career among the university and college going students and perception of student's career choice decision's making factor and other educational and Psychological variables. The career future of students directly link to the education and various disciplines this study indicates that a student's background and cooperation of teacher inside the school have a maximum impact on his career choice and decision making confidence. The review of the available literature illustrate that there are crucial depth of literature of research studies restated in influencable relation of career choice and teacher cooperation status among university and college going students are following below -

(A) Pillai and Nair (1970) : studied the "Living conditions of Graduate Teachers in Kerla" and that a majority of teacher's were from lower middle class. Even the point of view of educational background of their parents and other members of their families. Teachers generally came from middle class or upper middle class families.

The factors, which are more crucial in this field, like socio-economic status, values, attitucles, sentiment's likes and dislikes are likely to affect the inter group academic interaction and out of the classroom settings between teachers and students.

(B) Mishra, Agrawal and Tiwari (1992) : conducted study on the college students with reference to success and failure to assess their attitude towards their teachers.

They found that students belonging to the successful category had a positive attitude towards their teachers where as a negative attitude was observed in the failure group.

(C) Khan R.S. (1991) : has done important study on student perception of teachers as a function of educational level: academic achievement and school background of students. He has selected two types of schools namely Public and government and three educational level. that middle, lower secondary and higher secondary. Sample size was 300 hundred obtained results clearly indicated for inter school comparison that the students of the public school considered maintains discipline in the class as the most quality of a successful teacher and is punctual as the least important, which the students of government school gave first priority to the quality uses appropriate

strategies to make the lesson interesting and effective and last priority to provides guidance for future career. Second results shows that at the middle educational level in the public school the qualities maintains discipline in the class and is punctual and in the government school the qualities has good temperament and provides educational guidance were considered as the most important and least important qualities of a successful teacher. Further khan extended his study to assess the student's perception of the teacher's in fluency of school background, education level and academic achievement on the student's perception of the teacher. His study indicates that effect of school background of the students significantly affect student's perception towards teachers. No significant effect was seen on academic achievement of the students on their perception of the teachers. No significant effect interaction effect was also observed among school background academic achievement and educational level of students on perception towards the teacher.

(D) George Mathew (1976) : In vestigate a classroom behavior of teachers and its relationship with their creativity and self-concept. This presage process investigation was a descriptive co--relational study. The first set of presage variables includes creative teacher personality, creative teaching process and self-concept and second set included demographic variables such as age, sex, marital status, residential location and districts. The process variables were the dimensions of teacher behavior observed by the FIACS, direct/indirect (I/d) was the main criterion variables. Out of the total school populations of 245 teaching situations from thirty five schools were selected employing stratified random cluster sampling technique. There were 245 teachers were observed. The findings revealed the following facts.

- (a) There were no significant relationship between creative teacher personality and direct/indirect behavior of teacher.
- (b) There was no relationship between creative teaching process and behavior of teachers.
- (c) There was no relationship between creative teacher personality and other dimensions of teacher behavior.
- (d) There was no relationship between self-concept of teachers and their direct/indirect behavior.
- (e) There was negative relationship between self-concept of teachers and pupil initiation ratio and self-concept of teachers and 'vicious' circle creativity with self-concept.

(E) H.G. Desai (1978) : Investigated the perception of self and others as related to group membership of college students in sourashtra. The study aimed of finding out of the perception of self and others as related to group membership of college students. In this study they found that (a) all group reported favorable perception of themselves.

- (a) The college was seen less favorable by all the groups.
- (b) Opportunities for making friends perception of social activities received lowest positive perception.

(F) M.P. Bhasin (1974) : Studies the relationship of total school perception to academic achievement of students at high school level. Keeping in view the variables of intelligence self-concept, sex, socio-economic status and teacher perception of student's behavior.

Sample consisted of 200 students (100 boys and 100 girls) was selected randomly from high schools at phagwara, Pubjab. The major findings of the study were found that which are following;-

- (a) It was found that those high on academic achievement, intelligence, self-concept and SEs had high school perception and those found low on these variables had low school perception.
- (b) Girls exhibited high school perception as compared to boys.

Some significant studies have been made to uncover the influential relationship of career perception with scholastic achievement. A survey influential studies on creation of career perception and teacher cooperation inside the school. Therefore has to take into account both kinds studies on which attempts to identifying determine

of creation of career perception and other which attempts identify the effects of creation of career perception up on other career perception development variable. After that studies reviewed, how social well-being class structures to economic building blocks of career development and the teacher cooperation in side the school to secure decent work is considered.

Objective: The following objective has been formulated for the study:-

1. To study the teacher cooperation in-side the school in creation of career Perception.

Hypothesis: The following hypothesis has been made for verification. For this purpose null hypothesis has been used. *“Cooperation of teacher's will be a significant variable in creation of career perception”.*

Material and Methods

The present study aimed at investigating certain aspects of career perception with reference to socio Psychological characteristics such as teacher cooperation in-side the school and others variables specifically the study dealt with various educational disciplines.

Sample and procedure

In the present study respondents were randomly selected from various educational institutes. The study covers the state of M.P. and U.P. comprises a representative section drawn from three districts. The researcher identify sample frame, whose composition was decided on the basis of availability and accessibility criteria. Thus in sample selected respondents 240 male and female university and college going students of those districts on random basis. To measure the role of teacher cooperation in-side the school in creation of career perception and other Psychological variables and researcher has applied test developed by Mishra (1993) was used. It consists of 45 items on five points scale.

Results

Correlation is a variant analysis that calculates the strength of association between two variables and direction of the creation of career perception the results are completely quite clear for the university and college going students with respects to their stream of various discipline and different Psychological variables.

Table 1 : Mean, S.D. and Rank of students of various disciplines on teacher co-operation Scale inside the school.

S.N.	Disciplines	No. of Subjects	Mean (m)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Rank
1.	Medical	30	201.6	14.476	1
2.	Management	30	179.96	13.121	2
3.	Engineering	30	173.33	6.337	3
4.	Science	30	127.6	9.245	5
5.	Agriculture	30	132.4	7.089	4
6.	Education	30	127.26	8.076	6
7.	Fine Arts	30	117.3	2.680	7
8.	Arts	30	92.6	5.934	8

Efforts have been made to assess. The differentiation between the various disciplines regarding teacher's co-operation inside the school of students which is most valuable factor for creation of career perception and academic success. In this connection first of all mean S.D. values have been calculated for all groups. In the above table it is clear and it shows that the students belonging to medical discipline have achieved higher mean value (201.6) and first rank than their counter parts of other disciplines to teacher's co-operation inside school. Students belonging to master of business administration have secured second rank and students of engineering group have got third rank. It is clear from the above table that students of Agriculture group and science have secured fourth and fifth rank respectively. Whereas students of other disciplines have got lower scores than the others. It presents the importance of teacher's co-operation in selection of discipline and creation of career perception.

Fig 1: Mean, S.D. and Rank of students of various disciplines on teacher co-operation inside the school.

The trends of result is also presented in the perceiving graphical figure. It is clearly indicates the importance of teacher co-operation in school status preening the perception of career in creating positive and satisfactory way. It is inferred that the students belonging to Medical, Management, Engineering, Agriculture and Science disciplines have showed better teacher co-operation in school status than their other counterparts of education, Fine Arts and Arts group of students. It has been also tried to calculate difference of scores on teacher co-operation in school between the various disciplines observed results clearly shows that the students of Medical, Management and Engineering streams have showed better teacher co-operation than the other disciplines. These results are consistent with the recent researches investigating the influential relationship between teacher co-operation in school and career perception of students of various disciplines. This results indicate that in all of demographical structure, teacher co-operation in school has great influence on student's academic achievement and creation of career perception.

Interpretation

Present research findings indicate that teacher co-operation was emerged as a dominant factor in creation of student's career perception. Without support of teachers no one can get perfection in his perception of career. The students is dependent up on the teacher in a tightly organized social system of the classroom. Teachers are model to their students perceive there in ideal form. Thus it clear that the teacher is key factor for his students. Keeping this view in mind such factor was considered fruitful and beneficial for the present investigation. On the basis of findings it can be stated that the teacher co-operation in-side the school of the students of medical, management, engineering. Agriculture, Science disciplines were high than the other group of disciplines students from similar discipline have showed positive perception towards their career perception. It means perception of career creation is effected by student's teacher co-operation in-side the school. The higher co-operation of teacher in school of students provides satisfactory creation of career perception towards their disciplines. This trends of result is

supported by creational analysis where creation of career perception was significantly and positively associated with co-operation of teachers and behaviors. Another interesting dimension through which extends this investigation is to examine difference concerning the background of teacher's co-operation in school status gender and resident of university going students of various disciplines. The influential graphical figure represent with teachers co-operation in school background of students of various discipline have been found to have a strong impact or creation on students career perception with respect to various disciplines. Therefore the impact of teacher's behaviors in school of students might be further moderate by student's gender and student's resident's background, which could be tested using larger samples. The teacher behaviors in school working and creative mental ability, creation capacity is more and major predictor of academic performance and creation of career perception.

Conclusion

The present study analysis aimed to determine the role of teacher behavior status of students on career perception and Psychological perspective among the university and college going students. This research also shows that the importance of teachers co-operation in school in predicting students on career perception. Creation of career perception is a path that students want to become in future. Teacher's behavior in school status is considered an important of family structure as it indicates the social status, position, power and resources of family. Teachers support in-side of school socio economic status and intelligence have emerged significant predictors for positive creation of career perception. More positive perception have been found in the students of medical, management, engineering group than the students of other disciplines. But inferior creation of career perception has been observed the students of education, fine arts and pure arts group. Socio economic status of family reflects parents, educational and occupational attainment along with financial and social networking resources to which the students have assess. Teachers support and SEs significantly influences the students career perception and decision making capacity. Career perception and decision making capacity being very difficult in a student's life. Students get highly influenced by their surroundings that may influence them to expose their teachers support and behavior potential for their personal, social and career development. Career perception and decision making power is a growing issue all over the world and selecting appropriate career choice is a big opportunity for students especially at the various disciplines. The creation of career perception and decision making among the students of various disciplines is commonly influenced by their teachers support and behavior. The teachers support and behaviors status of the students of medical, Management engineering, Agriculture, and science disciplines were high than the other students group. Students of similar disciplines have showed positive perception towards their career perception and higher teacher's support of students provides satisfactory perception towards their disciplines.

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